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PARABOLIK TIPDAGI TENGLAMA UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada parabolik tipdagi tenglama uchun Koshi masalasi va uning xususiy yechimlari toppish qisqacha bayon etilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Koshi masalasi, xususiy yechimlar, issiqlik tenglamasi.

Bizga cheksiz to‘g‘ri chiziqda bir jinsli issiqlik tarqalish tenglamasi

$$u_t = u_{xx}, -\infty < x < \infty, t > 0 \quad (1)$$

berilgan bo‘lsin. (1) - tenglama uchun

$$u(x, t)|_{t=0} = x \cdot e^{-x^2} \quad (2)$$

$-\infty < x < \infty$ Koshi shartini qanoatlantiruvchi yechimi topilsin.

Dastlab, yordamchi

$$u_t = u_{xx} \quad (1),$$

$$u(x, t)|_{t=0} = \varphi(x), \quad -\infty < x < \infty \quad (3)$$

cheksiz to‘g‘ri chiziqda koshi masalasini yechamiz. Yechimni

$$u(x, t) = X(x)T(t)$$

ko‘rinishida izlaymiz. Bundan quyidagilarni aniqlaymiz:

$$u_{xx} = X''(x)T(t), \quad u_t = X(x)T'(t), \quad X(x)T'(t) = X''(x)T(t)$$

$$\frac{T'(t)}{T(t)} = \frac{X''(x)}{X(x)} = -\lambda^2, \quad \begin{cases} X''(x) = -X(x)\lambda^2 \\ T'(t) + \lambda^2 T(t) = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$X''(x) + X(x)\lambda^2 = 0$$

bu tenglamaning yechimi quyidagidan iborat:

$$X_1 = e^{-i\lambda x}, \quad X_2 = e^{i\lambda x}.$$

Endi ikkinchi tenglamani yechaylik:

$$\frac{dT}{T} = -\lambda^2 dt \Rightarrow \ln T = -\lambda^2 t + C \Rightarrow T(t) = e^{-\lambda^2 t} * C$$

$$u(x, t) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} u_n(x, t) = \sum_{\lambda=-\infty}^{\infty} T_\lambda(t) X_\lambda(x) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} A(\lambda) e^{-\lambda^2 t} \cdot e^{\pm i\lambda x} d\lambda$$

Bunda λ ixtiyoriy xaqiqiy son, shuning uchun soʻnggi integralda $+$ ishoraligini olamiz.

$$u(x, t) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} A(\lambda) e^{-\lambda^2 t + i\lambda x} d\lambda$$

Yordamchi masala (3) shartiga koʻra $t = 0$ da

$$\varphi(x) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} A(\lambda) e^{-i\lambda x} d\lambda$$

Furye almashtirishini qoʻllasak,

$$A(\lambda) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \varphi(\xi) e^{-i\lambda \xi} d\xi$$

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, t) &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \varphi(\xi) e^{-i\lambda \xi} d\xi \right) e^{-\lambda^2 t + i\lambda x} d\lambda = \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\lambda^2 t + i\lambda(x-\xi)} d\lambda \right) \varphi(\xi) d\xi \end{aligned}$$

Ichki integralni hisoblaymiz:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\lambda^2 t + 2i\lambda \frac{\sqrt{t}(x-\xi)}{2\sqrt{t}} - \frac{i^2(x-\xi)^2}{(2\sqrt{t})^2} - \frac{(x-\xi)^2}{(2\sqrt{t})^2}} d\lambda = \\
 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{t}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\left(\lambda\sqrt{t} - \frac{i(x-\xi)}{2\sqrt{t}}\right)^2} d\left(\lambda\sqrt{t} - \frac{x-\xi}{2\sqrt{t}}\right) e^{-\left(\frac{x-\xi}{2\sqrt{t}}\right)^2} = \\
 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{t}} \sqrt{\pi} e^{-\left(\frac{x-\xi}{2\sqrt{t}}\right)^2} \\
 u(x, t) &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{\sqrt{t}} e^{-\left(\frac{x-\xi}{2\sqrt{t}}\right)^2} \varphi(\xi) d\xi = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi t}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\left(\frac{x-\xi}{2\sqrt{t}}\right)^2} \varphi(\xi) d\xi \quad (4)
 \end{aligned}$$

Ichki integralni hisoblashda

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-x^2} dx = \sqrt{\pi} \quad (**)$$

tenglikdan foydalandik. Ushbu tenglikni isbotlash uchun $x = \lambda y$ ko‘rinishida ifodalaymiz. $dx = \lambda dy$ ekanligini hisobga olsak,

$$I = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-x^2} dx = 2 \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-x^2} dx = 2 \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\lambda^2 y^2} \lambda dy$$

tenglikni ikki tomonini $e^{-\lambda^2}$ ko‘paytirib, $(0, +\infty)$ integrallaymiz.

$$\frac{I}{2} = \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\lambda^2 y^2} \lambda dy$$

$$\frac{I}{2} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\lambda^2} dy = \int_0^{+\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} e^{-\lambda^2 y^2} e^{-\lambda^2} \frac{d\lambda^2}{2} dy$$

$$\frac{I}{2} = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{dy}{1+y^2} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\lambda^2(y^2+1)} d-\lambda^2(y^2+1)$$

$$\left(\frac{I}{2}\right)^2 = -\frac{1}{2} \int_0^{\infty} d \arctg y \left(e^{-\lambda^2(y^2+1)} \Big|_0^{\infty} \right)$$

$$\left(\frac{I}{2}\right)^2 = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{\infty} d \arctg y$$

$$\left(\frac{I}{2}\right)^2 = \frac{1}{2} (\arctg \infty - \arctg 0)$$

$$\frac{I^2}{4} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - 0 \right) \Rightarrow \frac{I^2}{4} = \frac{\pi}{4} \Rightarrow I = \sqrt{\pi}$$

Demak,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-x^2} dx = \sqrt{\pi}$$

(1) tenglama yechimini (4) dan foydalanib, Koshi masalasini yechamiz:

$$u(x, t) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi t}} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-\left(\frac{x-\xi}{2\sqrt{t}}\right)^2} \xi e^{-\xi^2} d\xi$$

bo'laklab integrallash natijasida, ushbu yagona yechim kelib chiqadi:

$$u(x, t) = \frac{x}{\sqrt{(4t+1)^3}} e^{-\frac{x^2}{4t+1}}$$